

Promoting an Inclusive Education through Collaborative and Dialogical Work in Mathematics Classes and in Research

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Abstract

Original Research Article

Inclusive education has been discussed since the Salamanca Statement (UNESCO, 1994). But despite its ideals being mentioned in legal documents, there is still a huge gap between discourses and practices. Diversity is a characteristic of human beings. Education should provide effective learning conditions to each pupil (Ainscow, 1999). Collaborative and dialogical work and research (César, 2009, 2013, 2017) were effective ways of empowering pupils who need specialized educational and social support (César, Machado, & Ventura, 2014). The *Interaction and Knowledge* (IK) project lasted 12 years and had a 10-year-follow-up. It used three research designs: (1) *quasi-experimental* studies; (2) action-research projects; and (3) case studies. We focus on data from Mathematics classes and in the action-research projects. The participants were 69 teacher/researchers and the pupils from around 600 classes, their families, other educational agents, four researchers, and internal and external observers. Several data collecting instruments were used, allowing for the triangulation of sources, data collecting instruments, researchers, and theories, used as quality criteria (Denzin, 2002). The analysis of some paradigmatic examples from blind pupils and another one with a slower cognitive and emotional development illuminate that the implicit messages and the inter-empowerment mechanisms play an important role in their mathematical performances and life trajectories of participation. Collaborative and dialogical work and research were important features to promote an inclusive and intercultural education, increasing these pupils' autonomy and legitimate participation (Lave & Wenger, 1991).

Keywords: Inclusive Education, Blind, Slower Cognitive And Emotional Development, Collaborative And Dialogical Work And Research, Mathematics Learning, Empowerment, Equity

INTRODUCTION

The Challenges of Inclusive and Intercultural Education

One of the most vulnerable and socially undervalued minorities attending schools and challenging them are the pupils who need specialized educational and social support (e.g., Deaf, blind, autists, or other conditions). In legal documents they are usually designated as having Special Education Needs (SEN), but in the IK project we designate them as pupils who need specialized educational and social support (César, in press; César et al., 2014). To promote inclusion, these individuals also need social support. Otherwise, they cannot be autonomous, and autonomy is a characteristic of empowerment. Thus, to achieve an inclusive and intercultural

education and society, we must provide them with the educational and social supports they need to develop their abilities and competencies. This means enlarging the scope of what inclusion is: education and a society for all (César, in press).

In Portugal the first legal educational document (ME, 1991) that underlined the rights of SEN pupils, as they were then designated, appeared before the existence of the inclusive paradigm (Ainscow, 1999; UNESCO, 1994). At the time the integration paradigm separated SEN pupils in special schools. Thus, they did not meet those from mainstream schools and were often negatively compared with so-called "normality". But in the early 90s, Ainscow (1991) was already discussing the best features so that mainstream schools would be effective for

all pupils. Many years earlier, in 1956, in Portugal, João dos Santos, a psychoanalyst and pedagogue, began a school, called *Centro Infantil Helen Keller*, in which blind, low vision and non-blind pupils learned together (Carvalho e Branco, 2000). Thus, even before the inclusive paradigm (UNESCO, 1994), there were some examples of inclusive schools, and inclusive pedagogues, *avant la lettre*.

The Portuguese Constitution (AR, 2005) is a statement against all forms of discrimination. Although clearly addressed in discourse, educational practices and daily life experiences are still full of examples of gender and cultural discriminations, including the ones experienced by those who need specialized educational and social support. Thus, 30 years after the Salamanca Statement (UNESCO, 1994), the issues concerning inclusion are yet to be solved.

These persons often acknowledge that they need to overcome more barriers, and fight for their rights (César & Ainscow, 2006; César et al., 2014). What these minorities have in common with other undervalued cultural minorities is the feeling of being powerless, of not having a voice (Apple, 1995; César, in press), or not being allowed to have a legitimate participation (Lave & Wenger, 1991). Thus, all these vulnerable minorities are facing power issues and how they will solve these issues shapes their life trajectories of participation (César, 2009, 2014; César et al., 2014). Promoting intercultural dialogue, namely through bi-univocal cultural mediation (César, 2017), is an important feature to construct learning communities and facilitate school achievement. Becoming empowered is an essential step to promote an intercultural and inclusive education and society.

Armstrong, Armstrong, and Barton (2000) underlined that, in an inclusive paradigm, diversity cannot be seen as something to avoid or fear. Inclusive education should be “celebrating the difference”. César (2024, in press) and César and Machado (2024a, 2024b) discuss several examples in which different approaches, reasonings, and solving strategies, in Mathematics classes, contribute to improve pupils’ learning, and development. The inclusive paradigm also avoided exclusion and “narratives of difference”, as mentioned by Billington (2000). This is more than respecting diversity: it is celebrating it, using it as an advantage. It also promotes empowerment, self-esteem, resilience, and facilitates tracing life trajectories of participation in which pupils’ abilities, competencies, needs, and interests play an important role. Thus, promoting an inclusive and intercultural paradigm is the most effective way to celebrate everyone’s potentialities, and to develop the pleasure of thinking, that Zittoun (2023) considers an essential step to promote learning and development, at different ages and in different contexts.

Inclusive education principles state that pupils in a SEN condition should attend mainstream schools, near their homes, facilitating their socialization (UNESCO, 1994). Hence, having reference schools for certain conditions is not what corresponds to the inclusive education principles. But in Portugal there is a lack of human and material resources, as the Government does not allocate much money to Education. For many years, in cities

and big towns there were schools known for their “specialization” in some condition (César, 2012). This was an informal movement: a sensitive Directive Board from a mainstream school attracted teachers, other educational agents, and psychologists, who wanted to work with a particular condition. Then, parents and pupils chose to go to that school because they would have better human and material resources. Thus, the law just made official what was already happening (AR, 2008).

This was an easy move in cities and big towns, which are mainly on the coast. But it was much more difficult in the countryside away from the coast, where many blind pupils do not attend reference schools for the blind, because these schools are distant and public transports are not available. In smaller towns, and in villages, it is difficult to have the technological tools to turn ink documents into Braille documents. Thus, many blind pupils do not have access to tasks and evaluation materials in Braille. They have someone who reads them out loud, but they feel constrained to ask her/him to read again and again, and they clearly have no equity when we analyse the possibilities of autonomous reading of non-blind pupils.

This law (AR, 2008) introduced two new main issues: (1) Some conditions were not considered; and (2) In some regions there are no reference schools. There are reference schools only for: (A) blind and low vision pupils; (B) Deaf; (C) autists, and (D) multiple disabilities and pupils who are Deaf/blind. Other conditions (e.g., Down syndrome) were not considered and pupils who had specialized educational support according to the previous law (ME, 1991) lost their rights. Thus, sensitive issues were not addressed in this law and are still being discussed to this day.

For blind pupils, as well as for other pupils who need specialized educational and social support, the need for empowerment, agency, equity, and social justice is quite clear (César & Ainscow, 2006). Organizational details play a very important role in their academic performances (Ainscow, 1999; César, 2012; César & Santos, 2006), and in their life trajectories of participation (César, 2014; César et al., 2014). Inclusive education is only possible when equity, empowerment, agency, legitimate participation, and autonomy are guaranteed (Allan & Slee, 2008; Armstrong et al., 2000; César & Ainscow, 2006; Skovsmose, 2019). Thus, there is still a long way to go if we want to achieve an inclusive education and society.

Dialogical Self, Social Representations, and Diversity

We assume the Self as dialogical (Hermans, 2001, 2003) and multi-voiced (Bakhtin, 1929/1981), and culture and learning as situated (Lave & Wenger, 1991). This means that the context, scenario, and situations (César, 2014) in which learning takes place shape pupils’ performances (Cobb & Bauersfeld, 2012; Cobb & Hodge, 2007), and their life trajectories of participation (César, 2009, 2013, in press; César et al., 2014). As Rose (2002) claimed, the curriculum can be used as a tool for inclusion or exclusion. The tasks teachers use to operationalize the curriculum, the evaluation instruments, or the didactic contract they establish, facilitate power distribution, or concentrate power in teachers’ hands.

Hermans (2001) conceived of the dialogical self as composed by several I- and Me-positions that interact among themselves. The I-self is a knower, and the Me-self a known. Time and space are the two main dimensions (Hermans, 2001, 2003). The dialogical self relates the past and the present but also creates expectations for the future. The relation between past, present, and future expectations shapes the life trajectory of participation (César, 2009, in press; César et al., 2014). In each moment (time) and situation (space) the dialogical self is organized in a particular architecture in which some I-positions are dominant (e.g., when I am at work in an important meeting, my I-position as worker becomes dominant).

Some I-positions (as mother/father, worker, husband/wife, daughter/son, pupil, member of a club) create conflicting interests (e.g., needing to go on working and wanting time to play with my children) that may cause suffering, or guilty feelings. If the conflicts between the different I-positions are mild, people experience levels of suffering they can manage. If these levels are too strong, people can experience mental health issues. Those participating in vulnerable and socially undervalued minorities tend to experience higher conflicts between the different I- and Me-positions (César, 2014, in press; César et al., 2014). Sometimes suffering becomes unbearable for them, particularly at school, and they give up (e.g., they do not try to answer an academic task; they drop out of school). Me-positions (how the others see me, and how I believe they see me) are also affected by conflicts. Me-positions are particularly important for self-esteem, namely in the family, neighbourhood, and at school. Inter-empowerment mechanisms can be first used in the family context (César, 2009). But when this does not happen, or when there is a need for educational and social specialized support, it is even more important to use them in the school context, to promote agency and legitimate participation (César & Ainscow, 2006; César et al., 2014).

The different I- and Me-positions shape social representations (Marková, 2005), namely how pupils see themselves as Mathematics learners (Machado & César, 2012, 2013). Using dialogism in the school context proved to be an effective way to promote positive academic social representations, agency, and pupils' academic performances (Ligorio & César, 2013). Kumpulainen and Lipponen (2010) also underline the importance of dialogical inquiry to develop productive interactions that promote agency. Dialogic teaching and learning play an essential role to promote pupils' agency and legitimate participation, particularly when they need specialized educational and social support (César, 2014; César & Calado, 2010; César et al., 2014; Davies & Renshaw, 2013).

Collaborative and Dialogical Work in Learning Improvement

Many authors underline the importance of social interactions in the teaching and learning processes (César & Kumpulainen, 2009; Cobb & Bauersfeld, 2012; Kumpulainen & Lipponen, 2010; Ligorio & César, 2013), namely, to promote empowerment, legitimate participation, agency, and to increase pupils' performances. Sfard (2008) goes even further as she states that thinking is communicating, and César and Machado (2024a, 2024b) illustrated how L1 shapes mathematical

approaches, reasoning, and solving strategies. César (2009, 2017, in press) states that social interactions among peers have a positive impact on academic self-esteem and in life trajectories of participation. But to increase its effects, pupils working in dyads or in small groups need to work in their Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), facilitating competencies that are part of their potential development to become part of their actual development (Vygotsky, 1934/1962). It is also important to choose academic tasks that allow pupils to act alternately as more competent peer (Vygotsky, 1934/1962). Another important feature is the existence of thinking spaces, a concept coined by Perret-Clermont (2004), that refers to spaces in which pupils feel safe enough to talk, ask questions, express feelings, and doubts.

Collaborative and dialogical work is a powerful tool to promote rich peer interactions, pupils' learning and development, and their empowerment and autonomy (César, 2024, in press; César & Kumpulainen, 2009; Civil, 2007; Cobb & Bauersfeld, 2012; Ligorio & César, 2013). Working in dyads, and then in small groups, facilitates the establishment of peer interactions, followed by a fruitful whole-class discussions (César, 2024, in press), in which pupils confront different ideas and argumentations, or reasoning and solving strategies. Among the IK team, and sometimes including other participants, when we were discussing interpretations, theoretical issues, or decisions regarding research, we were not looking for consensus, but for improvement of the theoretical background and practices, both in teaching and in research (César, in press; Ventura, 2012). This means we conceived of collaborative work in a dialogical way (Renshaw, 2004), where conflict also exists and is important for learning and education, where critical analysis and confronting different points of view is an essential feature.

The analysis of peer interactions and of whole-class discussions illuminated the importance of power issues (Apple, 1995; César, 2024, in press; Civil, 2007; Cobb & Hodge, 2007). Pupils whose families used inter-empowerment mechanisms since they were children, showed more resilience, higher academic self-esteem, and more leadership. For those whose families did not use inter-empowerment mechanisms, using them in class was an essential step to increase their self-esteem and academic performances. In the IK project we decided to use them since the first week of classes. Accepting different approaches to problem solving, mathematical reasoning, and solving strategies was used as an inter-empowerment mechanism (César, 2024, in press; César & Machado, 2024a, 2024b). Then, on the second class, during the whole-class discussion, every pupil went to the blackboard to explain a solving strategy in which s/he was successful. The implicit message – every pupil could do Mathematics – had a strong impact. This was one of the first inter-empowerment mechanisms we used in classes. Later, pupils internalized the inter-empowerment mechanisms, transforming them into intra-empowerment mechanisms they used in an autonomous way, in other situations.

Being empowered promotes agency and acting as a legitimate participant of the learning community (Lave & Wenger, 1991). It also shapes life trajectories of participation. This construct

includes three important dimensions: (1) time (it lasts a whole lifetime, having different moments); (2) space (it is a trajectory, happening in different contexts, scenarios, and situations); and (3) participation (because we all act as legitimate or peripheral participants in each situation). Collaborative and dialogical work is important to promote life trajectories of participation that correspond to pupils' abilities, competencies, interests, and needs. It is also important to develop an intercultural and inclusive education, that promotes equity and more social justice (César, 2009, 2013, in press; César & Machado, 2024a, 2024b).

Outside classes, schools need to use regulatory dynamics of participation to empower vulnerable, socially undervalued minorities (César, 2013). When these regulatory dynamics are only decided by the mainstream culture, where power is not distributed but used from top to bottom, we called it univocal cultural mediation (César, 2017). This lack of empowerment explains why many good intentions fail: if those who have no agency feel they are not listened to, respected, and appreciated, they tend to ignore cultural mediation. When power is shared, the suggestions and decision-making include a team from both cultures, where all participants can act as legitimate participants and work collaboratively and in a dialogical way, we call it bi-univocal cultural mediation (César, 2017). This is the format that proved to be more effective, and to have more long-term positive impacts (César, 2024, in press).

But when we think about power seriously (Apple, 1995), we also need to be aware about what counts as legitimate knowledge in class (Abreu, Bishop, & Pompeu, 1997; César, 2024, in press; César & Machado, 2024a, 2024b; Cobb & Hodge, 2007; Civil & Hunter, 2015). This is decided by those who have more power. In class, that usually corresponds to the teacher. But what happens in class is also shaped by scientific knowledge, particularly the one disseminated through scientific journals and books. However, in the academic world power issues are seldom discussed, as Apple (1999) showed. Power affects journal reviews but often reviewers are not aware of that. César (2010) discussed how power is used in academic scientific events and in research, underlining that these issues are usually ignored. Hence, there are many power issues that affect learning, even among adults, which require further discussion. In every context, scenario, and situation in which there are social interactions, or decision-making, power plays a most important role, shaping agency, self-esteem, and life trajectories of participation. Being aware of the power issues is an essential step to promote more social justice and equity in schools, in society and in the academic world (César, in press; Skovsmose, 2023).

Culture, Power, and Vulnerable Minorities

We use the concept of culture in two different senses: (1) in a large sense; and (2) in a strict sense (César, 2014). When we refer to Portuguese culture, Cape Verde culture, or the Deaf culture (written with capital letters), we are using culture in its large sense, and the mother language (L1) associated to each culture plays a very important role in its characterization. The L1 is one of the main features shared by those who participate

in that culture, and it is essential for their feeling of belonging and for their social interactions. Members participating in each culture share values, traditions, religion, ways of dressing and cooking, particular types of music and art, among other things (Nieto, 1996, 2018).

But we also use culture in a strict sense (written with small letters), for instance when we talk about the school culture (César, 2013) or the classroom culture (Cobb & Bauersfeld, 2012). The language of instruction is not what characterizes a school or classroom culture. Many schools share the same language of instruction, but they develop different school cultures. Many schools include members participating in different cultures in a large sense, which means that there are educational agents and pupils with different traditions, religions, ways of dressing and cooking, among other features. Thus, it is what the educational agents and pupils from that school share (e.g., educational principles, rules, patterns of understanding what is going on, codes, ways of acting and reacting) that characterizes that school culture. It is the existence of that common ground that makes them feel accepted or rejected, powerful or powerless, acting as legitimate or as peripheral participants (Lave & Wenger, 1991).

The Deaf culture is usually assumed as a culture in a large sense because it has its own language (Portuguese Sign Language – PSL, in Portugal; other Sign Languages in other countries). We assume that blind culture is also a culture, but in a strict sense. It does not have a particular language, as blind people share the L1 of the family and/or country in which they live. Thus, from the oral point of view there are no huge differences between them and non-blind people. But they use a particular symbolic system to read and write: Braille. Moreover, they need to know and understand the physical and social world around them without using one of the five senses: vision. Using this symbolic system and having no access to vision also create understandings, barriers, ways of thinking and feeling, that are shared and understood among blind people. Thus, in a strict sense, there is a blind culture.

Blind Pupils' Needs

Using Braille brings new challenges to the school system, teachers, and pupils, particularly if we aim to promote an intercultural and inclusive education, and to empower pupils. Teachers who teach blind pupils are more effective if they know Braille. But although Braille is not difficult to learn, only a few teachers, even in reference schools for the blind (AR, 2008, 2018), know Braille. On top of that, the Portuguese Ministry of Education does not always place teachers who know Braille in schools with many blind pupils or in reference schools for the blind (César, 2012). Teachers' placement does not consider any extra pre- or in-service education (e.g., in Braille, or PSL). In short: the existing human resources are not enough and those who exist are often wasted. This creates difficult situations for blind pupils that could be avoided if the intercultural and inclusive principles (UNESCO, 1994) were respected in teachers' placement in schools.

Blind pupils need to have access to textbooks, tasks used in class, and evaluation instruments (e.g., written tests, exams)

that are in Braille (Santos, 2008). That is the only way to promote equity and social justice, because they need to be able to read those materials in an autonomous way, and as many times as they need. Although this has been assumed in a legal document since 1991 (ME, 1991), and reinforced by other legal documents (AR, 2008, 2018), there is a huge gap between what is written and the school practices. Many textbooks do not exist in Braille, only some of them have audio versions, and many teachers do not provide the materials they use in class in Braille. Teachers who choose the textbooks in each school are seldom sensitive enough to consider the needs of blind pupils.

The Braille system uses a cell with six points, which may, or may not, be prominent, creating 63 possible combinations (Santos, 2008), allowing the letters of the alphabet, numbers, and punctuation to be written. A particular sign before a word means that there is a capital letter. Braille Mathematics has some particularities. The Braille cell does not allow for writing fractions with a numerator on top and a denominator on the bottom, like the ones non-blind people use. So, an extra bracket is needed to write a fraction in Braille. When teachers do not know Braille, they may not understand the difficulties that blind pupils face, as they do not master the particularities of this culture in a strict sense, which are shaped by the symbolic system used to read and write (César, Ventura, & Machado, 2013; Santos & César, 2009; Ventura, César, & Santos, 2010). In class, they may say sentences that are confusing for blind pupils. Blind pupils who are Portuguese, and whose families are also Portuguese, speak Portuguese as their mother language (L1). But as they read and write in Braille, a particular symbolic system, their oral communication in Mathematics classes has different characteristics which are shaped by that system's specificities. When analysing the resolution of a task on complex numbers, in the 12th grade, Santos (2008) and Santos and César (2008, 2009) also highlight specificities of those who use the Braille system and are blind, illuminating how the relationship established with the teacher and colleagues, as well as the interactive process, are essential for these pupils to feel welcome and valued, promoting their access to academic achievement.

Since Portuguese blind pupils share the L1 of their families, friends, teachers and many of their classmates, socialization is usually easy. They share social activities with other children or teenagers and are often invited for birthday parties and similar events. When teachers have experienced pre- and in-service education that prepared them to teach blind pupils, they adapt tasks so that these pupils participate in the same ones as their classmates. Even in Arts, in Physical Education or in Science Labs it is possible to adapt the tasks, if the teachers have developed their know-how concerning the blind condition. But many teachers have never participated in an effective teacher education which would prepare them to deal with specialized educational support, well-adapted to the needs of the blind. Consequently, quite often, their learning opportunities are not the ones they should experience, and there is no equity in school practices, which means disrespecting what is written in the legal documents (AR, 2005, 2008, 2018).

The existence of a blind culture is quite clear in a sentence we heard from João dos Santos. Carvalho e Branco (2000) quoted it: "The horizon – I learned from the blind – is what is far away within the reach of the hand" (p. 57), a definition of horizon that only someone who sees with his/her hands, and not with his/her eyes, could give. For this reason, seeing with the hands also creates a culture in a strict sense, a particular way of understanding the world. This sentence was stated before the inclusive paradigm existed. But it shows an inclusive positioning *avant la lettre*, as João dos Santos considered that non-blind people could also learn from the blind.

Pupils With a Slower Cognitive and Emotional Development

An inclusive and intercultural education is the best educational resource to facilitate learning for all pupils, but it is even more important when pupils have slower cognitive and emotional development. Many times, these pupils are not accepted by their classmates, particularly when they also have motor and/or language difficulties. In Portugal these pupils have the right to educational support and special evaluation (AR, 2008, 2018). Sometimes, they attend a mainstream school and class, but they solve different tasks, and at the end of the cycle they get an attendance certificate instead of a diploma. As a result, their vocational and professional opportunities are reduced. This means that any decision regarding special measures should be made carefully, and parents need to be aware of its consequences. But although this is clearly stated in legal documents, it is not always put into practice. As César (2012) and César and her collaborators (2014) have claimed, it is just as dangerous and penalizing not to signal a need for educational and social support as it is to over-signal it, ignoring the abilities and competencies that this pupil is able to mobilize.

Psychologists' and doctors' reports should focus on what that child or teenager is able to do, instead of only identifying what they cannot do (César et al., 2014). César (2012) advocates for the need to produce a "functional diagnosis", at least in three different contexts (school, family, and leisure). A functional diagnosis describes and explains how that person functions while performing different tasks, and what her/his possibilities of progression are in those different contexts. A functional diagnosis provides several examples of what that child or teenager can do autonomously, or with help, and of the types of tasks that are well-adapted to make him/her work in his/her ZPD (Vygotsky, 1934/1962), inside and outside classes. It also points out how the individuals in each context may facilitate his/her learning achievement and development. As this diagnosis is produced after observing the child or teenager in different contexts, talking with those who contact him/her in those contexts, and analysing his/her performances in different tasks, it allows for the confrontation of his/her performances and ways of acting and reacting in each context and situation. Thus, we identify if the child or teenager shows difficulties in just one context or in all of them, facilitating the understanding of what creates those difficulties (e.g., if a teenager uses mathematical reasoning in daily life situations, but not at school, probably this is not a cognitive issue, but it may be an emotional or social issue related to his/her school experiences).

Teachers need to know what are the abilities and competencies that pupils mobilize, as it is upon these that new knowledge can be constructed. As César (2012) underlined, having access to a functional diagnosis that provides examples of how they can work with that pupil is an essential step to increase her/his learning and development. All the specialists involved in supporting that child or teenager (e.g., doctors, psychologists, teachers, pupils, and their families) need to communicate and work collaboratively, finding a common language that is not too hermetic, so that they can share decision making, and interpret and understand what each one of them means (César, 2012; Farrell, 2006). If a report is only understandable by colleagues with the same job, then it seldom contributes to increase learning at school.

This also illuminates why the concept of Personal Performance Shapers – PPS (César, 2024) is so useful to elaborate a functional diagnosis and to know how to teach these pupils. In the school context, instead of focusing only on school marks, as teachers usually do, it combines them with the abilities and competencies that pupils are already able to use in an autonomous way, as they are part of their actual development (Vygotsky, 1934/1962). Thus, knowing pupils' abilities and competencies from the first week of classes allows teachers to adapt tasks that promote their potential development (Vygotsky, 1934/1962), and to give pupils the opportunity of working in their ZPD. This is an important step for all pupils, but it is even more relevant for those with a slower cognitive and emotional development.

Usually, psychologists' reports are based on psychometric tests. But these tests are not adequate for these pupils. Usually, the reports they produce only confirm their failures, but do not show any possible path for progression. Using developmental instruments is much more appropriate. Unfortunately, there are only a few instruments with these characteristics, and often there is the need to create new ones, like the one the IK team developed (César, 2024; César & Machado, 2024a, 2024b; Machado, 2014). This is an essential move if we want to promote an inclusive and intercultural education, because identifying the abilities and competencies that are part of the pupils' actual development, and those which are part of their potential development, is the best way to promote their learning and development (Vygotsky, 1934/1962).

Quite often these pupils have already experienced exclusion in different contexts, scenarios, and situations. Many times, they are rejected by their peers, both in and out of school. Sometimes they are also excluded by certain family members, and some families tend to do less activities with them outside their home. Thus, showing these pupils what they can achieve – and showing it to their classmates as well – is a way of empowering them, promoting their self-esteem, agency, learning, and development (César, 2014, 2024; César et al., 2014; César & Santos, 2006). Often, their families read so many negative expectations in the reports that their own expectations are also low. However, inclusive education aims at developing as much autonomy as possible. Therefore, accurately identifying the abilities and competencies that can be developed is an essential

step to promote the best schooling and professional life trajectories of participation.

Ernest (2024), reflecting on ethics and Mathematics Education, raised several questions that are even more important when we assume an inclusive and intercultural education. When teaching pupils who need specialized educational and social support, discussing how to teach them, how to facilitate learning and development, is a central issue. But we also need to make decisions about pre- and in-service teacher education and to adapt it to pupils' characteristics, interests, and needs. Teachers' education should be practical, discussing examples, using case studies, role-playing, and observation of classes that are discussed afterwards. Wanting to do is different from knowing how to do. Thus, know-how is an important issue if we aim at promoting an inclusive and intercultural Mathematics Education.

METHOD

The *Interaction and Knowledge* (IK) project lasted 12 years (1994/95-2005/06) and had a 10-year follow-up that allowed us to better understand its impacts in pupils' life trajectories of participation (César, 2009, 2013). The follow-up had three conditions: (1) once a year (June/July), for 10 years; (2) every five years (thus, two times in total); and (3) one single time, after 10 years. In each condition all the pupils answered a questionnaire. Six of them were chosen, at the beginning of the school year, to be interviewed. An analysis of the complete *empirical corpus* was only possible when the follow-up ended (June/July 2016). Then the meta-analysis began, and some new constructs were coined (César, 2017, 2024; César & Machado, 2024a, 2024b). The *empirical corpus* is very rich. So, we are still doing this job.

The IK included three research designs: (1) *quasi experimental* studies; (2) action-research projects; and (3) case studies (Hamido & César, 2009; Ventura, 2012). These three research designs allowed for an in-depth study of the IK main goals: (1) to study and promote collaborative and dialogical work in formal educational scenarios; and (2) to promote an intercultural and inclusive education. The IK team also worked collaboratively and dialogically. Hence the use of the pronoun “we” when we write. We assumed an interpretative paradigm (Denzin, 2002). We focus on data from the action-research projects as Armstrong and Moore (2004) considered them particularly adequate to do inclusive research.

Participants

The main participants were the pupils who participated in the IK project (5th to 12th grades, around 600 classes from all over Portugal), 69 mathematics teacher/researchers, and four psychologists. Other participants were pupils' families, the Directive Board and other educational agents, and external observers. The external observers were chosen among those who did not believe in collaborative and dialogical work, cultural mediation, and inclusive education. The variety of participants allowed for the triangulation of the sources. The 73

researchers contributed to the triangulation of the researchers' (interpretations). These interpretations were also triangulated with pupils' interpretations, as we also used collaborative and dialogical work as a tool for research (César, 2013; Hamido & César, 2009; Ventura, 2012).

Data Collecting Instruments

In the first week of classes, data was collected through a task inspired in projective techniques (TIPT1), a questionnaire (Q1), and the IACC (*Instrumento de Avaliação de Capacidades e Competências*), which evaluates pupils' abilities and competencies related to Mathematics, and was elaborated by the IK team (Machado, 2014). Data collecting instruments also included other questionnaires (Q), tasks inspired in projective techniques (TIPT), interviews (I), informal conversations (IC, in presence or by email), observation (O, audio and/or videotaped), teacher/researchers' diary (D), reports from external (ER) and internal (IR) observers, and documents (DOC). We use these abbreviations in the excerpts (e.g., I5 means the fifth interview). Thus, we also triangulated the data collecting instruments. In research using qualitative data treatment and analysis, triangulations are important quality criteria (Denzin, 2002; Hamido & César, 2009).

Procedures

Data were collected for a minimum of one school year. Trainee teacher/researchers or those at the start of their career changed school every year. Other teacher/researchers were already part of the board of their school and could follow the same class several years (2nd cycle – 5th and 6th grades; 3rd cycle – 7th to 9th grades; secondary schooling – 10th to 12th grades). Thus, some classes participated in the IK for three or more years.

When a class included pupils who needed educational and social specialized support (e.g., blind, Deaf) we used to read the reports from previous years concerning those pupils before the beginning of the school year. During the first week of classes, we aimed at knowing the pupils better. So, we used TIPT1, Q1 and the IACC. Documents were also collected before the beginning of the school year (e.g., school educational project) and during the beginning of the school year. The first interview (I1) took place at the end of the first term (mid-December). Q2 and TIPT2 were used in the first class of the second term (beginning of January), and Q3 and I2 at the end of the school year (June/July). All the other instruments were used during the whole school year. The follow-up questionnaires and interviews also took place at the end of the school year (June/July).

Data treatment and analysis was based on a narrative content analysis (Clandinin & Connelly, 1998) from which inductive categories emerged. It allowed pupils' life trajectories of participation to be traced. We used successive readings, and interpretations were produced by several researchers, as well as by the pupils' themselves when they read their excerpts and interpretations. In the excerpts, using ... means a very small pause, (...) means a longer pause, and [...] between two talks means that a part of the interaction was cut.

We wanted pupils to be anonymous. Thus, in the first papers we used the first letter of their names, like in César (2014), where we analysed a paradigmatic group designated as A., J., N., and T. In papers referring to the same dyad in other moments (time) and situations (space) we used the same designation (César, 2014, 2024, in press; César et al., 2014; César & Santos, 2006). But soon we understood that we had too many participants to use just the first letter of their name. So, we decided to use a name distinct from the real one, chosen by the pupils themselves. Sometimes they chose the name they liked best, others another name that began with the same letter of their real name, or they used any other criteria.

Pupils gave permission to use any excerpt of their interviews or any other instrument. If they told us we could not use it, or part of it, we deleted that part of the paper. They read each interpretation concerning their participation. Sometimes they suggested complementary discussion, or a different analysis. Other times, they asked us to also use another excerpt besides that. This means that for the IK team what is usually called "informed consent" is much more than merely giving authorization to use their data before beginning the research. We wanted to promote pupils' empowerment and agency also regarding the research (César, 2024, in press; César & Machado, 2024a, 2024b). Thus, writing was also a collaborative and dialogical process, which made it slower, and did not favour high productions of papers, as demanded by metrics used in academics' evaluation.

RESULTS

We analyse data from two different schools and two different vulnerable and socially undervalued minorities: (1) blind pupils; and (2) those with a slower cognitive and emotional development. These schools were quite different and the barriers each minority faced were also differentiated. The school attended by blind pupils did not use cultural mediation. The one attended by J., a pupil with a slower cognitive and emotional development, began using bi-univocal cultural mediation when the IK project worked there. As this school had different issues from the one analysed by César (2013, 2024, in press), cultural mediation focused on other priorities. Its Directive Board and many teachers wanted parents to come to school when they were asked to. But as usually they were only asked to come when there were disruptive ways of acting, or underachievement, they hardly ever turned up. Thus, the IK team suggested two different measures: (1) to ask parents to come to school at the beginning of the school year and meet the tutor of each class to discuss the life trajectory of participation of their daughter/son, particularly from a vocational and professional point of view; and (2) to bring experts to talk about themes that interested pupils and their families. The first measure corresponded to asking parents to come to school to discuss their children or teenagers' future, which was a positive issue. The second measure aimed at transforming each term meeting into a more appealing event. Pupils and their families completed a small questionnaire during the school enrolment process, and they identified three themes they would like to know more about. Then, the school organized the meetings at

the end of each term in a different way: before or after those meetings, there were conferences with experts who engaged with the audience on themes of interest to them (e.g., being a mother/father of a teenager, teenagers' sexuality, drugs and alcohol abuse, racism, domestic violence, or vocational choices). The participation of the experts and the possibility of asking them questions, orally or written and anonymous, made these meetings successful. Teenagers were also very interested in them and mentioned this in many informal conversations (César et al., 2014).

The IK team realized that if they wanted to change practices and develop collaborative and dialogical work, promoting an inclusive and intercultural education, they needed to change the first week of classes. The main goals of this week were: (1) to know pupils' abilities and competencies since the first week; (2) to build trust between the teacher/researcher and the pupils, and among them, crafting thinking spaces (Perret-Clermont, 2004); (3) to manage to get all pupils working; (4) to increase the working rhythm but maintaining an easy-going working atmosphere; and (5) to spread the implicit message that each pupil was able to do and learn Mathematics. These goals corresponded to the kind of classroom community – a learning community (Civil, 2007), where each one was respected – that we wanted to promote, and that could favour pupils' Mathematics learning, and their development.

To achieve these goals, the IK team designed a first week in which teacher/researchers explored no new contents but focused on social interactions and implicit messages. S/he briefly explained they were going to work in a different way (dyads or small groups) to facilitate their learning. They would work in dyads in the 1st term (September to December) and in the first class of the 2nd term (January), they would choose if they wanted to go on working in dyads and small groups. But the team knew that discourses would not persuade pupils, particularly those who were long-time underachievers and had a low academic self-esteem. So, they elaborated tasks that were not rejected by any pupil, and that would get all of them working.

The first one was TIPT1 and the instruction, written on the blackboard, was: "Draw or write what Mathematics is for you". They received a blank A4 sheet and could use it in the vertical or horizontal position. Usually, surprised faces looked at the teacher/researcher. Some asked if they could really draw, others if they could draw and write; a few were more provocative (César, 2009, in press), but when they got their teacher/researcher's calm answer, they began working. Thus, soon all the pupils were working. On many classes that happened for the first time. The second task was a short questionnaire (Q1) about the subjects they preferred, the ones they liked less, how they described themselves as Mathematics learners, how they used their leisure time, and what were their future dreams, and plans (in and out of school). This was another kind of task no one rejected.

Then, pupils answered the IACC (César, 2024, in press; César & Machado, 2024a, 2024b; Machado, 2014). Once again, they were astonished, because these were not common mathematical tasks. They could not use a calculator, but they could draw, do schemes, use sums, anything that explained their reasoning, and

they could also choose which task they would solve first. Those who rejected Mathematics, sometimes said they could not solve any task. But when the teacher/researcher smiled kindly, pointed at Task C, and said: "I'm sure you can", they began working. Then they read Task D and either they answered it or tried another one. Thus, by the time they left the first class (50 minutes), they had already realized this was a different teacher and those were special Mathematics classes. They were also aware and amazed that the whole class was working hard and in silence. In many classes, this was a completely new experience for them.

In TIPT1 many blind pupils preferred to write what Mathematics was for them, but some chose to use the materials the teacher/researcher brought and that allowed for a visual representation of what Mathematics was for them. They used a cork sheet, pins, wood, paper, and other materials and produced geometrical figures, graphs, and even some three-dimensional figures. Sometimes they complemented them with a written text. Q1 was also in Braille, and blind pupils answered on their computer. Thus, blind pupils felt respected and appreciated from the first week of classes. The same happened in the IACC: it was in Braille, and they had relief figures when they were needed. Blind pupils had more time to answer the IACC, as stipulated by law concerning any assessment instrument (AR, 2008, 2018; ME, 1991).

During the second class every pupil went to the blackboard to explain a successful solving strategy and reasoning related to one of the tasks, or part of it. Some declined to go, but when the teacher/researcher gave her/him her/his answer sheet and told her/him s/he had a very interesting resolution, they changed their mind and went to the blackboard. For many of them, who were underachieving in previous grades, this was the first time they went to the blackboard in Mathematics, or that they could show a successful solving strategy, watching their colleagues copy it to their notebooks. They also realized – many times quite astonished – that the same task could have many successful solving strategies, explored in parallel on the blackboard, and that they were all accepted. Thus, the implicit messages "Each one of you can do and learn Mathematics", and "you can learn from each other" were powerful, and these inter-empowerment mechanisms began changing their self-esteem, their social representation about themselves as Mathematics learners, and their mathematical performances. This first week, and above all the class in which they all went to the blackboard, was often mentioned as a "turning point" in interviews, questionnaires, or informal conversations, even in the follow-up. Many of them stated they took pleasure in explaining their solving strategies, and they never forgot what they learnt on that day. Thus, this different first week of classes played a fundamental role in developing their pleasure of thinking, a feature that Zittoun (2023) claims to be essential to promote learning, at all ages and in diverse contexts.

Blind Pupils: Using A Different Symbolic System

This school was in an upper middle-class area. Pupils and their families were mainly Portuguese or from other European countries. Those who participated in cultures from outside Europe were from a wealthy context. Parents were

literate and usually had well-paid and socially valued jobs, or even money enough to live off income. This was a residential area, with many villas and luxury flats. As a secondary school, it was attended by pupils from the 7th to the 12th grades (12/13- to 17/18-year-olds, if they did not repeat any school grade). Due to these characteristics, its population was seen by the school Directive Board and teachers as “homogeneous and not problematic” (DOC, school educational project). Thus, this school did not put into practice any regulatory dynamics of participation between schools and families (César, 2013), namely concerning blind pupils and their needs. There was no cultural mediation. Although existing several power issues, they were not questioned, and pupils’ empowerment was not discussed. Thus, those who felt powerless faced higher difficulties to overcome barriers.

This school was known for having several blind pupils. But this did not mean that many teachers knew Braille. The teacher/researcher was one of the rare teachers who knew Braille. In Mathematics, using Braille creates some differences that teachers need to remember when they talk to the whole class. For instance, a fraction is indicated by an extra bracket. Thus, when solving equations, or fractions, if the teacher says “now, remove all the brackets”, blind pupils will have no more fractions, and they will feel lost when the teacher’s message goes on. Being aware of the characteristics of the Mathematics Braille is essential to empower blind pupils and to facilitate their access to achievement. The next excerpt illuminates the frustration of a blind pupil, usually considered idle, because her teacher does not know Braille:

It’s so frustrating! I keep trying to explain to my Maths teacher that fractions, for me, use extra brackets and she doesn’t care. She confuses me so much, that this year I’m experiencing difficulties and I even had a negative mark when I went to the blackboard. It’s as if we’re speaking different languages. What a mess! I feel unable to use even what I already knew... or to calm down and think... She keeps telling me that I don’t make any effort, that I don’t care or pay attention. It’s so unfair and the worst thing is that I’m unable to calm down and prove to her I know [Mathematics]. (...) I would love to be more resilient, to fight for my rights... But instead, I shut down and my teacher uses her words to attack me. (S., 15, 10th grade, 3rd year of the follow-up, June 2000)

Her account illuminates how teachers’ comments and lack of awareness of Mathematics Braille can be harmful for pupils’ performances, self-esteem, and life trajectories of participation. In Portugal there is a *numerus clausus* to enter university. In many colleges you need top marks in Mathematics to be admitted. Thus, when pupils begin struggling with Mathematics in secondary school (10th to 12th grades), they put at risk the vocational choices and the professional careers they want.

S. used to get top marks in Mathematics until the 9th grade (Level 4 or 5, the top ones). But in the 10th grade she is struggling, and she feels frustrated because she had her first negative mark in Mathematics. She wanted to become an informatic engineer, but if her marks in Mathematics are lower,

she will not be admitted to college. She wanted to be able “to calm down and think”, so that her mathematical performances could become better. But she is so stressed, she feels unable to do so. She is not able to use the intra-empowerment mechanisms she internalized, and that she was able to use when participating in the IK project, when she was taught by a teacher/researcher who knew Braille (7th grade), or in the 8th and 9th grade, in which she had another teacher, who did not know Braille, but who talked to her and tried to understand Mathematics Braille special features. This illuminates how important teachers’ ways of acting and reacting are in pupils’ performances.

Although phrasing it in a different way, because she never uses the words power or empowerment, S. states that she needed to be more resilient and able to fight for her rights. Thus, she needed more agency and to feel more empowered. That corresponds to being able to use her intra-empowerment mechanisms, like she did before. She recognizes her teacher’s way of acting as a verbal aggression, which implicitly means that she is aware there is more power on her teacher’s side. But she is not able to change that unbalanced interactive pattern and she feels desperate, because her Mathematics performances are not improving. The episodes described in this excerpt show a top-to-bottom use of power by her teacher, disrespecting blind pupils’ needs. Thus, this is the kind of discourse that does not contribute to an inclusive education, to social justice or to equity in Mathematics learning.

Her teacher’s way of acting is also creating conflicts in S.’s dialogical self. Her I-position as a Mathematics learner conflicts with her I-position as a girl, a daughter, a sister, and a friend. As a Mathematics learner she feels powerless, and not resilient. But in other situations, she often acts as a leader. Moreover, as a blind person she faced many barriers and used to be resilient and to fight for her rights. Her Me-positions are also conflictive, as the way her Mathematics teacher sees her – lazy, not caring about studying and about her marks – does not correspond to the way she sees herself as a learner. These conflicts are stressful for her, and she just wishes she would know how to overcome them. Another important issue is that she states that she began by explaining the characteristics of Mathematics Braille, but as her teacher insisted on ignoring them, she became unable to go on explaining her needs as a blind pupil. Quite often, when pupils are transformed into peripheral participants (Lave & Wenger, 1991), they lose their voices and are unable to express how they feel.

Another account, from Ricardo, shows that more empowered pupils react differently when teachers ignore their needs. Ricardo was born blind, and his parents used a lot of inter-empowerment mechanisms since he was a baby, as they reported in several informal conversations. They looked for adapted activities and games for him, and when they did not find them in the market, they produced them. For instance, they made a special Mikado for him in which different sticks had different textures, instead of different colours. So, he could play and develop his fine movements with his fingers, his fingers’ sensibility, and his computational competencies, because he had to sum up the points. They taught him how to run on the

beach. They developed his spatial orientation, so that he became more autonomous. He learnt music (piano, then guitar and singing) from a young age.

When he went to school, he had already internalized some inter-empowerment mechanisms, transforming them into intra-empowerment ones. He could use them in an autonomous way, in different situations. When he was four years old, he went to a well-known Portuguese school, specialized in blind and low vision pupils. More than one third of the school population was blind or had low vision, and the school had been conceived by João dos Santos, a renowned Portuguese psychoanalyst and pedagogue. It provided a stimulating environment for the blind. This school had many teachers who knew Braille, numerous adapted materials, and very creative practices, that empowered pupils and improved their autonomy. Ricardo was there from kindergarten to the end of the 9th grade (the school had no secondary schooling).

An example of inclusion was observed when the IK project coordinator went with teachers and 1st graders (6 or 7-years-old) on a Saturday morning visit to the underground stations. This visit was not part of the IK project, so there were no video cameras or tapes. But she always carried paper and pens. The new underground stations had many sculptures, coloured tiles, and famous sentences by well-known Portuguese artists and writers. The explicit goal was to explore the stations from the artistic point of view. The implicit goal was to promote autonomy by showing those children how they could use the underground. When there were sculptures, blind children explored them with their hands, and they discussed them with their non-blind peers. When there were coloured tiles, the non-blind children described them to the blind. One of them (João) said that some tiles were pink, and a blind child (Miguel) asked him:

1. Miguel – What’s pink?
 2. João – It’s a colour. Do you know what colour strawberries are?
 3. Miguel [smiling] – Yeah, they’re red!
 4. João – And do you know what colour whipped cream is?
 5. Miguel – I love it... It’s white.
 6. João – Right! So, imagine that you smash some strawberries very well in a bowl, and then you get some whipped cream and mix it with the smashed strawberries... When they’re very well smashed and mixed, that colour will be pink...
 7. Miguel – Ah! I get it! If we put more strawberries, it’s dark pink; and if we put more whipped cream, it’s light pink.
 8. João – That’s it. You’ve understood it all...
- (Miguel and João, O, registered by the IK coordinator, November 1994)

This episode was not planned as part of the IK *empirical corpus*. But it constitutes such a fine example of inclusion, that it illustrates the wonderful work that was developed in that school, and it helps us understand why Ricardo, and many other

blind pupils, mention the impacts that attending this school had on their life trajectories of participation, and on their resilience, autonomy and positive self-esteem. The easy-going atmosphere, the natural way in which these two children interact, João’s ability to find an efficient way of explaining a colour to a blind peer, illustrate how important it is to have effective mainstream schools that know how to promote inclusion, and show, through their practices, that blind and non-blind children can study and live together in harmony. That they can teach and learn from each other, and that an inclusive society is a more balanced one. João knew Miguel and he knew he loved strawberries. He guessed he knew that they were red. Therefore, instead of feeling intimidated because he had to explain a colour to a person who was blind, he just found a way to make clear to Miguel what pink was.

Ricardo was in the 11th grade, and he always had top marks in Mathematics. But this year he was experiencing difficulties because his teacher often made gestures with her hands that he could not see them. When he asked for an explanation, she just told him “You should pay attention”. He replied: “I’m paying attention, but I am blind. I cannot see your gestures. If you do not explain in words what you are doing with your hands, or drawing on the blackboard, I cannot follow...” (Ricardo, IC1 by email, 11th grade, 1st year of follow-up, November 2006). He tried several times, but the discussions went on, with no pragmatic consequences. Thus, he decided to write us an email. In the 10th grade, he had a great relationship with his teacher from the IK project, and he knew the IK organized workshops for teachers. He thought that suggesting one could help teachers who did not master Braille to understand blind pupils’ characteristics and needs.

This pro-active way of acting shows that empowerment is directly connected to agency, and to legitimate participation (Lave & Wenger, 1991). It also illuminates that taking power seriously is essential to promote intercultural and inclusive education (Apple, 1995; César, in press), and that doing inclusive research means giving voice and agency to participants (Allan & Slee, 2008; Armstrong & Moore, 2004; César & Ainscow, 2006; César et al., 2014). Feeling unable to solve his conflicts in class, he tried another approach: someone from the outside and a workshop. This strategy proved to be effective. His teacher went to the workshop and, as usual, she was asked to blindfold her eyes and do several daily tasks or follow a teacher’s problem solving. This task was performed in two different groups: one of them was observing; the other was performing. Then, the groups changed positions. Afterwards, there was a whole-group discussion. For the first time, many of them realized that doing things without using their vision was much more complex, slower, and demanded a lot of effort. Thus, blind pupils had to exert much more effort than non-blind to follow teachers’ explanations, but also in their daily tasks. They had to be more organized, as they needed to use their time well. This means that Ricardo’s agency helped him, many other blind pupils from that school, and even non-blind who were also struggling to achieve in school, and to trace their life trajectories of participation, in and out of school. When teachers’ practices respect pupils’ needs, all of them improve, because teachers become more attentive and sensitive to diversity. Thus, ways of

acting that are adequate for blind pupils are also better for many other pupils.

The next example is from an 8th grade class and the teacher was using the Sieve of Eratosthenes (Appendix 1) to identify all the prime numbers up to 100. In César (2014) we analysed the same task but solved by another dyad in another class. The difficulties are similar for these two blind pupils, mentioned there and here. But in this excerpt Tânia (non-blind) was able to understand Rui's difficulties earlier and this made him feel confident and act as a legitimate participant (Lave & Wenger, 1991). The instructions asked them to erase (Braille) or to cross out (ink) all the numbers that were not prime numbers. The difficulty, for blind pupils using Braille, is that erasing means using your nail to make the small points of a Braille cell disappear. If you make a mistake, you can no longer make them appear again, while non-blind pupils can easily use a rubber if they change their mind.

[They read the instructions. Tânia starts to cross out the numbers that are not prime. Rui remains silent and quiet]

1. Tânia – Why aren't you talking to me? Why aren't you solving this?
2. Rui – I'm afraid of doing it wrong and afterwards I can't put it right again.
3. Tânia – You mean... if you erase with your nail, then you can't write it again?
4. Rui – [He smiles] Yeah...
5. Tânia – But if we speak out loud, you'll only erase when we agree...
6. Rui – I think that 3 is prime... But I think 4 is not, I can divide it by 2... Do you agree?
7. Tânia – I agree. [He erases 4 with his nail] And 5 is also a prime number. So, we don't erase it. And 6?
8. Rui – I can divide it by 2 and 3. It's not prime, we erase it. But 7 is prime. We don't erase it. But 8, 9 and 10 are not prime and we erase them.
[Tânia writes quickly, but she knows Braille means more time to erase, and she waits for Rui]
9. Tânia – Right. The next prime is 11. We don't erase it...
10. Rui – Agreed.... 12 is not prime... but 13 is.
(Tânia and Rui, O, Audio taped, 8th grade, February 2005)

One of the interesting features of this dialogue is that, when they are solving the task, they have different things to do, due to the symbolic system each one of them uses: Rui uses Braille and he needs to erase the numbers with his nail; Tânia, who is non-blind, uses a pencil to cross out the numbers. But to facilitate Rui's performance, she always talks about "erasing" (Talks 7 and 9), which corresponds to his action, not to hers. She understands that it is more difficult to solve this task when you are blind and use Braille. Thus, she gives him more time to perform his actions (erase) and she waits for him before the next talk. She shows a very inclusive and intercultural way of acting. The other important issue is that Tânia quickly realized that Rui was silent, and he was not solving the task. But he usually worked well in Mathematics. So, she tried to find out what

might cause his strange way of acting (Talk 1) and as soon as he explains his fears (Talk 2), she understands that the different symbolic system he was using led to more difficulties than using paper and pencil (Talk 3). These first talks illuminate that Tânia knows Braille characteristics, which corresponds to mastering a different symbolic system. Zittoun (2006) stated that symbolic resources facilitate the transition of knowledge when individuals move to a different context. Thus, having classmates who are blind was an opportunity for Tânia to learn another symbolic system, and that promoted her development. Tânia's understanding of the Braille characteristics and of the difficulties it entailed had a positive effect on Rui (Talk 4) and her suggestion to erase only if they agree (Talk 5) allowed him to act as a legitimate participant since Talk 6. Thus, this excerpt is an example of the existence of thinking spaces (Perret-Clermont, 2004), in which pupils feel safe enough to express their fears and doubts, or to ask questions. It is within thinking spaces that they can change more easily from peripheral participants (Rui's position when silent and not working) to legitimate participants, showing their agency (Lave & Wenger, 1991).

This excerpt also illuminates the importance of collaborative and dialogical work to promote legitimate participation and more inclusive and intercultural educational settings. Working in dyads facilitated Tânia's understanding of the challenges of Rui's symbolic system. She understood his difficulties and knew she could learn Mathematics from him, because that had happened before. It helped Tânia and Rui to change some of their I-positions as pupils, and some of their Me-positions (Hermans, 2003). They both felt empowered and were able to use the intra-empowerment mechanisms they had been able to internalize (César, 2009). Feeling empowered promotes a positive (academic) self-esteem, and pupils' mathematical performances. This is important for all pupils, but it is particularly relevant for those participating in vulnerable minorities, like blind pupils.

An external observer participated in this class. As usual in the IK project, external observers were teachers who did not believe in collaborative and dialogical work, or in an inclusive and intercultural education. Therefore, if they reported interpretations that were like those of the IK team, that was strong empirical evidence. This external observer had been a Mathematics teacher for 20 years. Thus, his report is even more impressive.

I never taught blind pupils because I always avoided that. Some colleagues told me these pupils were easily distracted, had many doubts, and never wanted to discuss their resolutions with their classmates. Now, I've changed my mind, and I would like to teach them. But I also realized I need to learn Braille, to be effective. But I was amazed to observe how they interact, how their peers understood their difficulties and their way of working. I realized they are slower because they use their nails to erase and that takes longer. This was surprising. They mastered the concepts, participated in the whole-class discussion, and were able to answer their classmates' doubts. Now I understand why they had Level 4. It's not because they have a special evaluation,

it's because they are able to solve the same tasks, the same written tests, and they are top achievers.
(External observer, ER2, 8th grade, February 2005)

Participating as an external observer made him understand the particularities of doing Mathematics when you are blind and deconstruct some of the prejudices that he held about blind pupils. He felt motivated to learn Braille and to teach blind pupils. This is an important change, as there is a shortage of Mathematics teachers who know Braille, and several blind pupils participate in his school. For the IK team, contributing to deconstruct prejudices and to a more effective in-service teacher education is a goal, as inclusive education is only possible if there are teachers aiming at participating in it.

Watching classes and discussing them is a very effective way of contributing to teachers' in-service education, even when they have many years of experience. The other relevant issue is that he understood that these pupils had Level 4 through their own merit, and not because they had a different or easier written test, or evaluation process. Thus, observing these classes contributed to his development as a Mathematics teacher, and this is one of the aims of inclusive and intercultural research (Armstrong & Moore, 2004; César, 2024, in press). Inclusive research allows participants to learn and to develop themselves.

Pupils with a Slower Cognitive and Emotional Development: The Example of J.

When a teacher/researcher belongs to the school board s/he usually teaches that class during a full cycle (e.g., 7th to 9th grades). But in this class, a striking episode happened in the 7th grade: pupils were going out on a visit and J.'s classmates declared that they were ashamed of going with J. and that he should stay at school. Teachers tried to convince them otherwise, but they were not persuasive enough and agreed to leave without J. – strong empirical evidence of the lack of inclusivity. Up until the 8th grade, J. had been deeply rejected by his peers, but it was this episode that made the Directive Board ask the IK project to work with this class. Thus, J.'s class participated in the IK in the 8th and 9th grades (1995/96 and 1996/97). At the time, compulsory education was up to the 9th grade. That diploma made it possible to apply for a driving licence, to have a small business in their own name, or to apply for professional studies or higher secondary school (10th to 12th grades). Therefore, it was important to get the 9th grade diploma.

In the first week of classes, no new Mathematics content was introduced. Teacher/researchers aimed at getting to know pupils better and they used a task inspired by projective techniques (TIPT1), a questionnaire (Q1), and a developmental instrument to evaluate pupils' abilities and competencies (IACC). J. showed a very low self-esteem (Q1), a negative social representation of himself as a learner (Q1), but the IACC illuminated he had access to concrete reasoning, used geometrical reasoning and a solving strategy based on graphic representations to successfully solve a geometrical problem; he also knew what profit meant and was able to connect school Mathematics and real-life problems about selling and buying objects. Thus, he mobilized many more abilities and

competencies than his reports indicated. César (2024) detailed how the concept of Personal Performance Shapers (PPS) was fundamental to choose J.'s first dyad, and to explain J.'s achievement in Mathematics. Identifying which abilities and competencies were part of his actual development and which were in his potential development (Vygotsky, 1934/1962) was an essential step to promote his learning and his development. Knowing what he was able to perform in an autonomous way also allowed for careful preparation of the first mathematical tasks and decide how the teacher/researcher should act, as described by César and her collaborators (2014). Using role-playing in in-service teacher education proved to be a very effective way in more challenging classes, like this one.

Up until the 7th grade, J. had a special education measure that was very restrictive. He had a special education teacher near him in Mathematics classes and they sat at the back of the classroom. He only coloured drawings, and his evaluation instruments were very basic. The IK team discussed J.'s performances during the first week of classes and outside the school context. We were convinced that he would be able to learn and progress more without these measures. Therefore, he began doing the same tasks as his classmates and the special education teacher was no longer present with him in the classes (César et al., 2014). These proved to be very important features to promote his acceptance by his peers. Watching him answering the same tasks, going to the blackboard, answering his peers and teacher's questions, was a novelty for J., and for his classmates. But it slowly changed the way they saw him and, although rejection was clear in the first few classes, as illustrated by César and her collaborators (2014), no one would have known that J. had ever been rejected while listening to the 9th grade audio and videotapes.

In the 9th grade, pupils decided on the dyads and their spatial distribution in the classroom, as is usual when a class participates for the 2nd year in the IK. At the end of November, when these dyads were formed, T. explained to their teacher/researcher that she volunteered to work with J., and N. to work with A., showing they had understood the kind of peer they needed. They also sat these two dyads one after the other, so that they could be a small group, later. The next interaction took place when they were studying Probabilities, and it was the first time they worked as a small group. This is visible in some parts of the interaction which illuminate that T. knew J. better, and that A. was used to answering explanatory questions when she worked in a dyad with N.

J. feels at ease and reveals his doubts (Talks 1 and 3), showing that in this class there are thinking spaces (Perret-Clermont, 2004). T. suggests they should elaborate a scheme (Talk 2) and A. and N. agree with her (Talks 4 and 5). They are all so enthusiastic that they all try to complete the scheme on the answering sheet, and until Talk 10, they forget about J., and he does not participate in their solving strategy. This first bit is very quick, and J. is not talking, but he is following what they are doing, as we realize in Talk 14, when he explicitly tells them how they should go on. So, despite not talking, he did not feel excluded, as he knew T. cared about him, and his classmates already included him when solving tasks in classes, and even in leisure events, outside school (e.g., birthday parties, going to the movies or to a park near the school). However, his lack of

confidence is visible in Talk 12. But T., who had been working with him since mid-November, knew his lack of confidence, but had also learnt how to overcome it. Thus, in Talk 13, she asks him how they should go on, but she also respects his rhythm and when he does not answer, she asks another question, showing him that she believes he knows the answer. This is the same kind of acting pupils observed in their teacher/researcher, and it illuminates how inclusive ways of acting can be learnt through classroom practices.

Problem: At the school bar drinks are all sold at the same price. Ricardo likes drinking either orange juice or coke. Pedro always picks orange juice, coke, or pineapple juice. João drinks pineapple, orange, or passion fruit juice. What is the probability that the three friends go separately to the bar and without planning anything beforehand, pick the same drink?

1. J. – Do you know how to solve this?
 2. T. – I'd do a scheme!
 3. J. – A scheme? How?
 4. A. – I also think it might be... if we put the names of each of them...
 5. N. – Of course! We do one of those schemes with circles!
- [At this point there are already three pupils trying to write on the sheet. T. was the fastest to take the sheet and writes as she talks]
6. T. – Ricardo, Pedro, João...
 7. A. – Now...
 8. N. – Now you must put down what each of them drinks... with those arrows...
 9. T. – I think I'd do it this way: on R, which is for Ricardo, I'd say that he could drink orange juice [L – Laranjada, in Portuguese] or coke...
 10. N. – Right... and you can also just write L or C, to be faster!
 11. T. – Are you getting this, J.?
 12. J. – I think so...
 13. T. – So, do you know how to go on? [Silence] Can you tell us what to write now?
 14. J. – It's like we did with Ricardo... I mean... from Pedro's circle there are 3 lines, one for each drink: orange juice, coke, or pineapple [A – Ananás, in Portuguese], and we can also just put the first letter, to have a neater scheme!
 15. N. – Hey T., what a great teacher you are!?! [Laughter]

16. A. – I also know how to continue. Now we do the same for João. [Grabs the pencil and continues the scheme on the sheet]

(J., T., A., N., O, audio taped, 9th grade, January 1997)

Someone that reads this first part of the interaction is aware that J. has more learning needs than his peers, but s/he could never imagine how rejected he was until the 8th grade, and that his teachers' reports mentioned J. was not able to learn Mathematics. J.'s answer (Talk 14) is detailed and clearly shows that he had been quiet, because he is not as fast as his peers, but he understood every detail of their resolution. N., who tended to make evaluative comments, praises T. for being an excellent teacher (Talk 15), showing that he also recognises she learnt her way of acting by observing their teacher/researcher.

The IK team avoided evaluative comments. They may create dependency, and the team preferred to promote autonomy and self-confidence. Thus, the IK team aimed at developing intrinsic motivation, and the pleasure of thinking (Zittoun, 2023). But what was not tolerated in classes were negative evaluative comments, something N. produced quite often at the beginning of the 8th grade, particularly about classmates who were slower than him. Thus, only having N.'s positive evaluative comments during this interaction is a sign that he became much more inclusive and respectful towards diversity.

T. and N. were top achieving pupils. They were very competitive at the beginning of the 8th grade and only cared about themselves. While it is still clear that they are top achieving pupils, and faster than A. and J., now they also respect slower pupils, those who need more time to solve the tasks and to achieve. The main difference is that now they understand those pupils are also achievers, they just have a slower rhythm, and this is an important feature of being inclusive. As A. used to need to show N., when they were a dyad, that she also knew how to solve the tasks, she shows that in Talk 16. Thus, both J. and A. feel respected and at ease in this small group, and they want to act as legitimate participants (Lave & Wenger, 1991).

17. J. – So far so good. I've understood. But don't we have to give a number to show the probability?

18. N. – Of course, we do! But now it's easy. Look at this scheme we've done and see which is the only chance of them all drinking the same drink.

19. J. – Just the orange juice... only two drink coke and pineapple too.

20. T. – Right... and only João drinks passion-fruit juice (M – Maracujá, in Portuguese); so that's no good either.

21. N. – Then let's put a red circle on L, to show this is the only hypothesis that fits what we want... and we must put captions on this so the teacher understands what we were thinking! [They draw a red circle around the Ls]

Figure 1 – Scheme elaborated by this small group

(J., N., T., A., O, audio taped, 9th grade, January 1997)

J. does not always master the accuracy of the mathematical designations, but he is very interested in learning, and he wants to produce complete resolutions. Thus, in Talk 17 he states that they need to quantify the probability. N. agrees with him, and he suggests that J. could look at the scheme (Figure 1) to see which is the drink they all ask for (Talk 18). Once again, N. shows that they learnt how to ask questions, or make suggestions, instead of giving J. the answer. This illustrates that they work as a learning community (Civil, 2007), and that they can co-construct their resolutions, as mentioned by César (2013, 2024, in press) and César and Machado (2024a, 2024b) when they were analysing other dyads. As soon as J. looks at the scheme (Figure 1), he identifies L as the drink they all ask for (Talk 19), and N. suggests they put a red circle to make clear that L “fits” what is asked in this problem (Talk 21).

T., who wants to use accurate designations, asks if those are the favourable cases (Talk 22), and J. remembers that those are the ones that should be in the numerator, that he calls “top part of the fraction”. This is a fine example to show he felt at ease and acted as a legitimate participant. Sometimes he did not remember the accurate designation, but he found a way of expressing himself so that the others could understand what he meant. He did not feel rejected or intimidated by T. and N.’s wish to use the most accurate definitions. This is another example of an inclusive interaction and learning environment. Co-construction is also visible because they complete each other’s reasoning and solving strategy, like in Talks 24 and 25, when they talk about the possible cases.

T. has the best understanding of J.’s difficulties and ways of reasoning. So, she wants to check that he can quantify the possible cases (Talk 28), and N. accepts her suggestion (Talk 30). But J. makes a mistake (Talk 31) that N. is unable to understand. However, there is no negative comment, just a question that means he wants to know how J. summed up eight possible cases (Talk 32). Once again this is a way of acting that they often observed in their teacher/researcher, and that we also saw in other teacher/researchers from the IK team, even when they were interacting with top achieving pupils, like in César and Machado (2024a). Thus, probably T. and N. had seen, or even experienced, how these questions can be helpful, and they learnt how to use them.

T., who worked with J. in the last month and a half, quickly understood what he had done (Talk 33), and she does not let N. make any comment, to avoid confusing J. about what he needed to do. Thus, in Talk 35 she suggests that he think only about Ricardo, and she asks about the favourable cases, and then the

possible ones (Talk 37). This suggestion to divide the task in small bits, makes J. realize how to achieve it (Talks 36, 38, and 41), and soon the whole group is once again participating in the resolution.

- 22. T. – These are the favourable cases, right?
- 23. J. – Ah! I remember that! Those are the ones you put on the top part of the fraction, right?
- 24. N. – Yeah... But I don’t know if you can put it that way exactly... we have to look in the textbook and see if that’s the right definition...
- 25. T. – But we also need...
- 26. A. – ... all the possible cases...
- 27. N. – But with the scheme that’s easy to see them!
- 28. T. – Yeah, but let’s see if J. knows which ones they are.
- 29. J. – All the possible ones?
- 30. N. – Yes.
- 31. J. – If we count the bottom ones, they’re eight.
- 32. N. – Eight?
- 33. T. – Yeah... he talked about counting the drinks each one could drink!
- 34. N. – But...
- 35. T. – Don’t think everything out all at once. Think only about Ricardo. How many favourable are there?
- 36. J. – One. Drinking orange juice, which is what we marked with the red ball.
- 37. T. – And how many are possible for Ricardo?
- 38. J. – Two: orange juice or coke.
- 39. N. – Great!
- 40. A. – So, we write...
- 41. J. – $\frac{1}{2}$.

(T., J., N., A., O, audio taped, 9th grade, January 1997)

As soon as J. realizes that for Ricardo it is $\frac{1}{2}$, he quickly answers that for Pedro it is $\frac{1}{3}$ and for João it is the same (Talk 43). Thus, one cannot say that he was not able to learn Mathematics, as many of his reports stated up to the 8th grade. Sometimes he needed more time, others he needed suggestions or questions that made him think about what he was doing, but once he learnt, he was able to use those competencies in an autonomous way (e.g., in the individual written tests). Therefore, he was able to do and learn Mathematics once the adequate conditions were provided. But those conditions were easy to learn, and even his classmates were able to provide them, as we can see in this episode. Thus, the decision that the IK team discussed, and that his teacher/researcher assumed by letting him do the same mathematical tasks and answer the same evaluation instruments, proved to be the best one for him. But this also meant a lot of meetings at the Ministry of Education, many reports written by the IK coordinator and the teacher/researcher, and a lot of bureaucratic work, to prove that the restrictive measures that were decided up until the 8th grade were not the best for J.'s learning and development.

42. A. – Right!

43. J. – Ah! I see! For Pedro it's $\frac{1}{3}$ and for João it's $\frac{1}{3}$.

44. T. – Yeah.

45. N. – And to know the probability of all of them drinking orange juice, what do we have to do with those numbers?

46. A. – Multiply them!

47. T. – Well done, A.! This one was for you! Just to see if you were paying attention!

48. A. – Hey, I'm sorry. I didn't remember I wasn't supposed to answer first.

49. J. – Forget it, I realized that. If I go to the blackboard, I can explain everything well: I do the scheme and explain what each thing represents. Then, under each name I write $\frac{1}{2}$, $\frac{1}{3}$ and $\frac{1}{3}$ and at the end I show the calculation for finding the probability: $\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{1}{3} \times \frac{1}{3} = \frac{1}{18}$. So, there's one favorable case, which is all of them drinking orange juice, but there are 18 possible cases.

50. N. – Great! You're getting real clever!

(A., J., T., N., O, audio taped, 9th grade, January 1997)

When the group realized that J. understood the resolution, N. asked him to quantify the probability of the favourable case (Talk 45). But he asks a question that includes a second part, more explanatory, in a similar way to what César and Machado (2024a) discussed, when a teacher/researcher did the same to help a top achieving pupil who had made a mistake. This illustrates that in different schools and classes, the way of acting of the teacher/researchers who participated in the IK team had a common theoretical background, that shaped their practices

and promoted an inclusive and intercultural education. To be effective, practices need to be discussed, analysed, so that they can become natural, and be used in different contexts, scenarios, and situations.

The group is so enthusiastic about their resolution, that it is A. who answers N.'s question (Talk 46), as she is used to him asking her questions, to see if she is able to represent their dyad on the blackboard, during the whole-class discussion. This raises the only implicit negative comment (Talk 47), made by T., who wanted J. to answer that question. A. quickly apologizes (Talk 48), but it is J. (Talk 49) who calms down T., showing her that if he goes to the blackboard in the whole-class discussion, he knows how to explain everything. This intervention by J. illuminates his cognitive and emotional development because he quickly understood that it was important to avoid a conflict and that it was in his hands to achieve this. If someone confronts J.'s self-confidence and way of acting in this interaction with those described by César and her collaborators (2014) at the beginning of the 8th grade, it becomes clear how much progress he made in this year and a half. This illustrates how important it is to provide inclusive and intercultural education, so that pupils' potentialities can be transformed into actual development (Vygotsky, 1934/1962).

It is particularly interesting to analyse the next two excerpts of N. and T.'s interviews after discussing this small group interaction. In January of the 9th grade, J. was fully accepted and acted as a legitimate participant (Lave & Wenger, 1991). Thus, he had been empowered, first by his teacher/researcher and her way of acting, including the inter-empowerment mechanisms and the implicit messages she used; then, by his classmates, as we could see in the last interaction we discussed. But when we analyse N.'s first interview (I1), we realize how excluded J. felt until the 8th grade, and how negative the feelings of his peers were about him. Both N. and T. wanted to avoid having J. as his/her peer, in the first dyads. They confessed to feeling a very strong rejection towards J. at the beginning of the 8th grade. Moving from these feelings to the ones they have now shows that classroom experiences shape the kind of persons and citizens those pupils are, and will be, as adults. If they do not experience inclusive ways of acting, if they do not learn more about the classmates that have specialized educational and social needs, they do not know how to deal with them and accepting them is much more difficult.

T.'s excerpt is even more interesting, because this was mentioned in the third interview (I3), in December of the 9th grade, when she was already working in the same dyad as J., as she volunteered to be his peer. She claims that being with him at the beginning of the 8th grade would be a "total condemnation", but she also recognizes that saying that now "seems so cruel", as she really loves him. But she underlines that, back then, "no-one liked him, we just wanted him to go away", and if that teacher/researcher did not teach Mathematics to that class, J. could have given up because he was living an unbearable situation. However, she realizes that J. "really wants to learn" and that "he has every right to be here". This underlines the importance of teachers in the acceptance of

diversity, and in the promotion of inclusive principles, of equity, and of more social justice.

The last thing I wanted was to be put with J. So, I only felt at ease when I saw who my peer was. He wasn't anything special, but there weren't that many good minds in that class, and I never believed, from what I saw in the first week of classes, that the teacher would put me with someone who was a top achiever in Mathematics. (N., 11, 8th grade, December 1995)

If I'd been put with J. right from the start of the 8th grade, I think I'd have been scared to death. It wasn't a dyad it was total condemnation! [She laughs] I mean, looking back now that I'm so fond of him, it seems so cruel. But you know what it was like, right? No-one liked him, we just wanted him to go away. (...) I think if it hadn't been for the Maths teacher things would have become so unbearable that he would have given up eventually (...) but now I realise that would have been a pity, that he really wants to learn and also that he has every right to be here. I even offered to be his peer this year when we prepared the layout of the classroom that we have now. (T., 13, 9th grade, December 1996)

T.'s next account, from the same interview, shows that she became humbler after participating in the IK project. She knew she was a top achieving pupil, so she never thought she could learn anything from someone she believed "was silly". But she realizes that maybe that person was not so silly after all, as he could do things T. did not know how to do. She recognizes she accepts diversity better, and that the class became "so cool" that all the pupils felt sorry about splitting up in the 10th grade. In other words, someone who hated that class in the 7th grade, now just wished to go on in the same class.

I knew I could be a very good pupil. What I didn't know is that some mates who I thought were silly were also very good at things I didn't even know how to do. That was hard to take, but it made me accept everyone better. And that's what made our class so cool, where everyone likes to be. Even I, who hated that class in the 7th grade, I'm going to feel sorry when we enter the 10th grade and have to split up. (T., 13, 9th grade, December 1996)

When she had already finished the 10th grade, she participated in the follow-up. She continued getting top marks, but no longer appreciated very competitive classes. She describes something that was common, and that many other participants adopted: as there were four pupils from the 9th grade class, they formed two dyads and sat one behind the other, and so they went on working like in the 9th grade. This shows how strong pupils' adherence to collaborative and dialogical work was. Another interesting remark is that she is still in touch with J., who moved to a professional school. But she still cares about how he is doing, and they continue to organise leisure activities together. Thus, the emotional ties among them were strong enough to survive even when they went to different schools.

The marks have been great, but our class is so competitive... I've got no patience for that type of thing

anymore... fortunately there's three other mates from last year. We formed two dyads straight away and placed ourselves strategically... one behind the other... Luckily the teachers didn't notice... or maybe they just don't care about that... and they let us be. (...) Can you believe I've been in touch with J. over the phone to know how he's doing, and we've even had lunch together with a few other mates?! That was one hell of a class! I'll never have such a good one again. (T., 15, 10th grade, 1st year of the follow-up, June 1998)

Missing their 9th grade class was a common remark in questionnaires and interviews. J. also states this, and he believes he will never have classmates like those again. He describes the new school as a place where "each one fends for himself" and that environment as a step backward. However, his marks are not an issue. But he misses the people who really liked him, like the teacher/researcher and his classmates. So, despite experiencing academic achievement, he feels less included than in the 9th grade. His cognitive progress is still there; it is stable in time and can transition into other contexts, so he was able to conclude the 10th grade in the new school. But his emotional development makes him understand that the social interactions that he experiences there are quite different from those in the 9th grade class, and that he preferred the latter.

I really miss my 9th grade class. I don't think I'll ever have mates like those again. At the school I'm at now each one fends for himself... and I don't like it. It's as if everything's gone back. (...) The marks haven't even been bad. What I miss is someone who really likes me, like the Maths teacher and my mates from my old class. (J., 15, 10th grade, 1st year of the follow-up, June 1998)

In the 11th grade J. showed the emotional development he had started at the 8th grade even more. He distinguishes between "good and bad scars" and recognises that all of them hurt. But he understands that some of them made him stronger, more empowered, and helped him to heal and to like himself better. This excerpt illustrates how much his dialogical self has changed, and how his Me-position (how he sees himself) has become more confident. A person who can make such a reflection is capable of emotional development and of in-depth reflections on life experiences. This also contradicts what was written in J.'s reports and shows how penalizing school can be when pupils are not provided with a well-adapted education, that respects their abilities and competencies, promoting their learning and development.

Now I know there are good and bad scars. All of them hurt. And they made me angry and want to hit someone. Scars mean there were wounds, right? And a wound, hurts. You can pretend it doesn't hurt... act like a hero. But it does. Only some scars are good because they make us stronger. Less angry. Like the scars I cured in the 9th grade when people started liking me... and I... too... and I too liked myself more. (J., 16, 11th grade, 2nd year of the follow-up, June 1999)

J.'s parents were so used to hearing very low expectations when it came to his learning and development that they reacted in a

rough way when we first talked. They came prepared for the usual kind of discourse: that J. had a severe cognitive impairment (as written in several reports), was aggressive, unable to learn Mathematics, often getting into trouble with his classmates and teachers. So, when we told them that J. had many more abilities and competencies than the ones mentioned in the reports, that he was able to do and learn Mathematics, and that the best decision was to let him solve the same tasks as his classmates, they thought we were fools. Even when we showed his IACC sheet, they doubted that he had done those resolutions by himself. Therefore, as we wanted to develop his functional diagnosis (César, 2012), we decided to ask them questions about J.'s daily life and we became aware that he was able to go to shops near home and use money, to buy goods and cook for the family (he loved cooking), which also meant he could follow receipts and calculate quantities for a different number of people. We went on talking, and we showed them how much mathematical reasoning was involved in the tasks he solved in his daily life, and that his socialization in their neighbourhood was well-developed. Although still very suspicious, they understood we were not as foolish as they thought and agreed that we try our learning methodologies.

Changing to the same evaluation instruments and criteria as the other pupils was a huge challenge. But this was also the only opportunity to empower J., to improve his self-esteem, his socialization in his class and in school. And, above all, it allowed him to get the 9th grade diploma and go on studying and tracing a life trajectory of participation in which he would have a chance to be financially autonomous. We knew he would probably get Level 2 (negative level) in the first term. Even if he progressed a lot, much more than all his classmates, he had spent so many school grades without participating in the mathematical tasks that he needed to learn much more than all the other pupils. But he was sensitive to our expectations regarding his progress, he felt we were proud of his performances, and we hoped that would make him go on trying, and that he would achieve a positive level in the 2nd term. Time proved us right, as he achieved Level 3 in the 2nd and 3rd terms (8th grade), and even Level 4 in the 9th grade, including the final national exam.

You know, the first time I spoke to you, I thought you were silly or that you were making fun of us. I think I even treated you a bit badly... [The adjectives he used at the time were much stronger and more negative than these] My son being able to learn maths? Being able to take a course? Earning a living? It all seemed nonsense to me!... But there he is. Married, with children, with a job, living off his and his wife's money, like so many others. Who would have thought?... We really liked him, even as he was... when he was like that... more backward than the others. But I never believed it... never... And the pride I feel now, in what he's achieved... [Very emotional, he added] And the peace... you know... knowing that I can die with no worries, and he knows how to take care of himself... when his mother and I are no longer here. (J.'s father, IC, audiotaped by the researcher, June 2007)

This excerpt is from an informal conversation (IC) with his father, who met the IK coordinator by chance in the street. As she had just met up with J. for his last follow-up interview, she had a tape, and it was J.'s father who suggested she audiotape the conversation. By then, parents and pupils were aware of the papers we wrote, the conferences and workshops in which we used examples, and they wanted more pupils to profit from the work we developed. Thus, these suggestions were common, and often they taped the conversations with their cell phones, when there were no other means. In the last part, he mentions something that was very important to all the parents we worked with: to know that J. was able to take care of his life, that he had a family and a job, and that they could die in peace. Parents of children with a slower cognitive development frequently underline these worries.

His parents were very happy when they realized he could succeed, and even more when we got authorization from the Ministry of Education to change the restrictive learning measures he had, and to let him have a 9th grade diploma if he succeeded. By then we had already realized that he would like to take a professional cooking course. That course included a trainee period (3rd year) and its conclusion was equivalent to the 12th grade. J. finished it in 3 years, and after the trainee period his employee invited him to stay on, offering him a two-year contract. Thus, at the age of 19, he was already employed and earning his own money. He had a job he loved, clients loved his cooking, he went on being friends with colleagues from the 9th grade class and had a girlfriend. This was a much more successful life trajectory of participation than the one mentioned in any report we read, before working with him. Thus, he is a clear example of how important it is to know pupils' abilities and competencies, to evaluate them based on developmental instruments, instead of psychometric ones that are not adapted to these pupils' needs and characteristics. It also illustrates the importance of developing a functional diagnosis that make us understand pupils' potentialities.

External observers were astonished when they realized that pupils with learning difficulties worked well with their peers, and that it was beneficial for all pupils to have them in mainstream schools.

I have never believed that pupils with mental handicaps and major learning difficulties should be included in mainstream education. That's what led me to accept being an external evaluator of the project: I thought it was my duty to prove that what they wrote was benevolent, a kind of educational charity. But I must admit that I have learned a lot about pupils with SEN and what needs to be provided for them. Even J., who initially had so many difficulties, has progressed so much that if I saw him today for the first time, I wouldn't be able to imagine what he was like in October 1995, when I observed this class for the first time. What I saw, the persistence with which they worked, the clear resolutions on the blackboard, the depth and accuracy of the whole-class discussions, was not at all what I expected to watch. I expected easy and "lenient"

teaching, so everyone would get “good marks”. (External observer, ER3, May 1996)

This external observer, who had 25 years of practice as a teacher, agreed to be an external observer to prove these pupils should not attend mainstream schools. However, by the end of the 8th grade, she already recognized that they were able to produce clear resolutions, to participate in the whole-class discussions, and that the IK project evaluations system was quite demanding. Moreover, she claims that if she had only observed J. in May 1996, she could not have imagined how he used to be in October 1995. This is a very impressive statement about J.’s improvement in his school achievement and in his socialization. Thus, she changed her mind, and underlines she learnt a lot about SEN pupils’ needs, and how to provide them with a quality education.

This experience [as an external evaluator] made me question my own practices. Especially when I taught and when I spoke about SEN pupils. It often made me feel uncomfortable because I considered myself an excellent teacher. But I realized that I have a lot to learn, even with 25 years of teaching, so as not to harm these pupils. The thing is, in my pre-service education, in the conferences I attended, and in the research projects I participated in, no one ever prepared me for this. (External observer, ER7, May 1997)

By the end of the 9th grade, in May 1997, this teacher confessed that being an external observer made her question her practices. Despite considering herself “an excellent teacher”, she realized that she was not efficient when she taught “SEN pupils”, and that she was not fair when she spoke about them. So, she realized that she had a lot to learn about teaching them, and that her pre- and in-service education, and the other research projects in which she had participated, had not prepared her to know how to teach these pupils. This is a very interesting remark, because we are not talking about someone who did not try to learn more, who was not very active – she even participated in research projects. But this is also a fine example of the need to promote a more inclusive and intercultural pre- and in-service teacher education.

I had never seen a Mathematics class like that. I must confess that, when I volunteered to be an observer, it was because I didn’t believe it was possible for all the pupils to work with such a persistence, showing a willingness to solve tasks that were far from simple (...). What surprised me the most was the feeling that, if the teacher left the classroom, they would keep working in the same way, with the same commitment and, what’s more, with joy. (External observer, ER5, January 1997)

This last excerpt is from another external observer, with 15 years of practice. He did not believe that all the pupils working in dyads and small groups would engage in mathematical tasks in a committed way, trying to overcome their difficulties, showing persistence and accuracy. The last comment was also produced by many other observers: the feeling that if the teacher left the classroom, pupils would go on working in the same way. When this claim is made by someone who did not believe in

collaborative and dialogical work, it provides very strong empirical evidence. It illustrates that these pupils were using intrinsic motivation, that they were more autonomous, and that the IK goals and principles (Ventura, 2012) were achieved. The IK team wanted to promote an easy-going atmosphere, a class culture that included the pleasure of learning, and of thinking mathematically. But this had to be combined with high-quality mathematical performances, where accuracy was a must.

Final Remarks

When we analyse the whole *empirical corpus* of the IK project, the importance of conceiving a different approach to the first week of classes becomes evident (César, 2024; César & Machado, 2024a, 2024b; Machado, 2014; Ventura, 2012). Every pupil mentioned the importance of this first week during the time they participated in the project, follow-up, or even after it, as they sometimes write us emails in a spontaneous way. This was a capital feature of the empowerment process, particularly the second class in which every pupil went to the blackboard to explain a successful solving strategy or part of it. During this week the implicit messages were very powerful and played an essential role in empowerment. In previous situations, the implicit messages were used to make them feel powerless, as their reasoning and solving strategies were not accepted, or their different symbolic system (Braille) was not known and that created unfair comments regarding their performances. Thus, using inter-empowerment mechanisms since the first week, and making them visible to the pupils through teachers’ practices, was a very significant feature.

This diversity illuminates that collaborative and dialogical work, inter- and intra-empowerment mechanisms, bi-univocal cultural mediation, as well as intercultural and inclusive practices, are important features to empower pupils participating in vulnerable and socially undervalued minorities, whose positive self-esteem is low, and who often experience underachievement. This is particularly important when pupils need specialized educational and social support, like blind pupils and those whose cognitive and emotional development is slower. Moreover, these practices also promoted the performances, learning, and development of pupils who achieved and participated in the mainstream culture. This is essential from the pedagogical point of view.

The follow-up also proved to be a critical element. Several schools had other research projects going on. But as soon as data collection was finished, researchers vanished and there was no more contact. The follow-up gave us access to very relevant information we would not have if it had not taken place. But it also passed strong implicit messages to the pupils: that we really cared about them; their opinions and lives were important; collaborative and dialogical work went on; and they were still part of the research and had a voice in it. We aimed at producing an inclusive and multi-voiced research. Thus, the follow-up contributed in a very strong way to empowerment, as they could still express their argumentations, understandings, reflections, and feelings. They could talk about their life trajectories of participation even when they were no longer participating in the IK classes.

These contacts were mediated by time (pupils developed, were more mature, had other life experiences, their life trajectory of participation was longer, and they had other goals they wished to achieve), and by space (they were in other classes, schools, colleges, jobs, countries, and lived in different contexts, scenarios, and situations). Even for those who emigrated, the follow-up proved to be an important empowerment feature. But it was also an empowerment feature for the research team, as many understandings, and conceptualizations, came from the analysis of the data from the follow-up.

The IK conceived research as inclusive, intercultural, collaborative, and dialogical. It was a learning process for the IK team, and for the participants. Thus, voice was given to participants, and pupils contributed to parts of the decision-making. As César (2010) claimed, there is a lot of research on the Deaf, blind, and other vulnerable minorities, but they are seldom asked to be part of the research decisions, or to comment and decide about what is written in the papers and books. Thus, the way we conceived research was also an inter-empowerment mechanism, and many times participants showed their astonishment for being asked permission to use certain excerpts, and interpretations (César, 2013, in press). Not only practices were collaborative and dialogical, but also research, and this constitutes another feature to increase empowerment. Having agency in the research shaped pupils' performances, inside and outside the IK classes, and shaped their life trajectories of participation, particularly their self-esteem, resilience, observation, and critical sense. But it also shaped researchers' life trajectories of participation, as stated by Ventura (2012).

For the pupils, several features contributed to their cognitive, social, and emotional development: learning how to deal with challenging open mathematical tasks; participating in the bi-univocal cultural mediation that was implemented in some schools; learning how to build thinking spaces (Perret-Clermont, 2004) in which they felt safe to express their questions, arguments, feelings, and doubts; and developing abilities and competencies that they could use during their life trajectories of participation, even when they had already left school many years ago. Thus, empowerment not only shaped pupils' mathematical performances when they were participating in the IK classes. It shaped their life trajectories of participation and made them more aware of their own dialogical self and competencies, but also of when they needed to work collaboratively again to increase the chances of achieving their goals. What we learn at school through the implicit messages, the emotional, social, and cognitive competencies one develops, are important tools to face future situations. This is particularly important for those who need specialized educational and social support.

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trajectories of participation are shared endeavours. Thus, our gratitude goes to the teachers, pupils, families, other participants, and colleagues who made IK come true. Our special thanks to those whose excerpts are discussed in this paper, who critically read and completed our interpretations. Also special thanks to Sofia Coelho, a psychologist who studied and lived in London, bilingual in English and Portuguese, for her editing of the English language, and for understanding so well the IK work.

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Appendix 1 – The Sieve of Eratosthenes

Figure 1 – List of numbers in Braille

Figure 2 – Ink printed list of numbers

3. Um método muito prático de arranjar números primos foi idealizado pelo sábio grego Eratóstenes (275–195 A.C.). O seu método é chamado Crivo de Eratóstenes. Agora vão construir o crivo de Eratóstenes para saber todos os números primos até 50.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40
41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50

O procedimento consiste em eliminar todos os números que não sejam primos.

Figure 3 – List of prime numbers in Braille

Figure 4 – Ink printed list of prime numbers

3. Um método muito prático de arranjar números primos foi idealizado pelo sábio grego Eratóstenes (275-195 A.C.). O seu método é chamado Crivo de Eratóstenes. Agora vão construir o crivo de Eratóstenes para saber todos os números primos até 50.

1	(2)	(3)	4	(5)	6	(7)	8	9	10
(11)	12	(13)	14	15	16	(17)	18	(19)	20
21	22	(23)	24	25	26	27	28	(29)	30
(31)	32	33	34	35	36	(37)	38	39	40
(41)	42	(43)	44	45	46	(47)	48	(49)	50

O procedimento consiste em eliminar todos os números que não sejam primos.